
A STUDY OF THE SELF CONCEPT AMONG COLLEGE TEACHERS OF MUMBAI**Dr Rajeev I. Jha,***Assistant Professor**Bombay Teachers' Training College,**Mumbai - 400039***Introduction:**

Self-concept denotes self-awareness of the individual. Self-concept is best conceived as a system of attitudes towards oneself. It enables the individual to think, perceive and evaluate in a way unique to themselves. Baumeister (1999) defines self-concept as, "The individual's belief about himself or herself, including the person's attributes and who and what the self is". Lewis (1990) suggested that the development of a self-concept of self has two aspects: A) The Existential Self and B) The Categorical Self. Carl Rogers (1959) proposed that the self-concept has three different components: A) The view you have of yourself (self-image), B) How much value you place on yourself (self-esteem or self-worth) and C) What you wish you were really like (ideal-self).

Self-concept is one of the most dominating factors influencing the individual behaviour; on the other hand life experience too effect the self-concept. Successes and other pleasurable events in life lead to the enhancement of self-concept while failure, frustration and other denigrating experiences tend to lower the concept of oneself. Self-concept which originally was considered to be the keystone in non-directive counselling by Rogers, is now taken as of major importance in the field of education also, because it is observed that self-concept has close connections with some personal aspects like learning, motivation, attitudes, perception and adjustment which determine the academic and other successes of the individual in and out of the school.

The major aspects of self-undertaken for studies are mainly four: the perceived self which relates to what the person thinks he is, the ideal self is what the person would like to be, the real self is what the person actually is and the social self is how the person thinks other people perceive him. Large discrepancies between any two aspects of the self, spell out a maladjusted personality, showing little insight into oneself and having no self-confidence.

Review of Related Literature:

Guskey (1988) describes an exploratory study designed to investigate the relation between selected teacher perceptions past research has shown to be shared by highly effective teachers, and teacher attitudes toward the implementation of new instructional practices. Data were gathered through a questionnaire administered to 120 elementary and secondary school teachers immediately following a one-day staff development program on mastery learning instructional strategies. Results showed that measures of teacher efficacy, teaching affect, and teaching self-concept were significantly related to teachers' attitudes regarding the congruence, difficulty of use, and importance of the recommended practices.

Isabell Paulick, Jörg Großschedl, Ute Harms, Jens Möller (2016) investigated the factorial structure of pre-service teachers' academic self-concept with regard to three domains of professional knowledge (content knowledge [CK], pedagogical content knowledge [PCK], and pedagogical/psychological knowledge [PPK]). They analysed the relation between pre-service teachers' academic self-concept and their professional knowledge. Their results confirmed that pre-service teachers' academic self-concept is empirically separable into CK, PCK, and PPK. Furthermore, the self-concept scales were positively related

to the corresponding test scores in the professional knowledge domains.

Yeung, Craven and Kaur (2012) conducted a study wherein Australian teachers from urban and rural areas of the state of New South Wales were asked to respond to survey items on two predictors (teacher self-concept, valuing of learning) and three outcomes. Confirmatory factor analysis established the five latent factors. Structural equation modelling found significant paths from teacher self-concept to both student-centred and teacher-centred approaches but not beliefs about student ability. The positive path from valuing of learning to student-centred teaching was statistically significant but the path to teacher-centred teaching was not. The significant path from valuing of learning to beliefs about student ability was negative indicating that teachers who value student learning were less likely to believe in ability constraints. Therefore, teacher preparation programmes should enhance self-concept simultaneously with teaching skills and values and facilitate an advocacy for students' learning.

The researcher also experienced a need to survey the College Teachers in reference to their Self-Concept. Hence, the researcher undertook this study to facilitate their understanding of the same and enhance his role as an educator.

The problem of the study is stated as follows:

A Study of the Self Concept among College Teachers of Mumbai

Major Objectives of the Present Study:

- 1) To study the level of the Self-Concept of College Teachers of Mumbai.
- 2) To compare the level of Self-Concept of College Teachers of Mumbai with reference to their:
 - i. Sex (Female and Male)
 - ii. Academic Streams (Science, Commerce and Arts)

Null Hypotheses of the Present Study:

There is no significant difference in the mean scores of the Self-Concept of College Teachers of Mumbai with reference to their:

- i. Sex (Female and Male)
- ii. Academic Streams (Science, Commerce and Arts)

Research Methodology and Participants:

The present study was a descriptive research survey wherein 105 college teachers were surveyed. The student teachers of the researcher visited these schools personally for data collection. The participants who volunteered and returned the instrument completely filled were taken into consideration for data analysis. A standardised instrument, the Self-Concept Rating Scale (SCRS) standardised by Dr Pratibha Deo (2011), as described below, was selected as it served the purpose of the present research well. The entire data collection process was spread over two months.

The Research Instrument:

The Self-Concept Rating Scale (SCRS) standardised by Dr Pratibha Deo (2011), consists of check-list of various adjectives which cover almost all the important aspects of personality. The words are also divided into the different dimensions according to the connotation of the attribute and these dimensions are Intellectual, Emotional, Character, Social and Aesthetic characteristics. The check list can measure all the aspects, perceived, ideal, real and social self, of the individual and under each, the scores are obtained for each dimension in positive and negative classes. The Rating scale is on a 5-point scale; the five points being, very much like this' much like this, uncertain, not much like this and not at all like this. The main purpose of SCRS is to help persons in finding out and assessing what the individual thinks of himself and through the assessment, study many of the underlying problems of perception, motivation, learning and adjustment.

Usually subjects take about 15-20 minutes for filing up the List for one aspect. For the rating scale, the weightages for positive words for the five points of very much like, much like, uncertain, not like that, not at all like that are 4,3,2, 1 and 0 respectively and for a negative word also the weightage is the same way. The composite score is obtained by subtracting the total negative score from the total positive score. The neutral words are to be ignored in the scoring. Test-retest reliability coefficient was 0.89.

The Major Findings of the Present Study:

The collected data was tabulated and analysed both through descriptive and inferential analysis (t-test and One-Way ANOVA). The relevant descriptive statistics of Self-Concept with reference to the sex of the College Teachers and their Academic Streams is given below in Table – 1 and Figure - 1:

Table-1:
Descriptive Statistics of Self Concept of College Teachers

	Females	Males	Science Stream	Commerce Stream	Arts Stream
Mean	115.75	104.18	94.57	128.49	110.97
Median	117	108	97	128	107
Mode	138	122	89	138	91
Standard Deviation	27.07	25.56	25.74	22.81	21.25
Kurtosis	-0.47	0.49	-0.47	1.07	-0.13
Skew	-0.24	-0.58	-0.36	-0.75	0.42
Count	65	40	35	35	35

Inferential Analysis Interpretations:

Table - 2		
t-Test: Self-Concept of College Teachers – Sex –wise Comparison		
	Females	Males
Mean	115.75	104.18
Variance	732.91	653.43
Observations	65	40
Pooled Variance	702.81	
df	103	
t Stat	2.17	
P(T<=t) two-tail	0.03	Sig. at 0.05
t Critical two-tail	1.98	

The mean score for the Female College Teachers on the variable ‘Self-Concept’ (M = 115.75, SD = 27.07) is statistically significantly higher (t = 2.17, df = 103, two-tailed $\rho = 0.03$) than those of the Male College Teachers (M = 104.18, SD = 25.56). Thus, the null hypothesis (H_0-1) is rejected. The p-value indicates that the probability that the observed results are due to random chance is low.

Table – 3:						
One-Way Anova: Self-Concept of College Teachers – Academic Stream wise Comparison						
SUMMARY						
Groups	Count	Sum	Average	Variance		
Science	35	3310	94.571	662.370		
Commerce	35	4497	128.486	520.492		
Arts	35	3884	110.971	451.676		
ANOVA						
Source of Variation	SS	df	MS	F	P-value	F crit
Between Groups	20135.37	2	10067.69	18.48	0.00	4.82
Within Groups	55574.29	102	544.85		<.0001	
Total	75709.66	104			Sig at 0.01	

Table – 4:		
Tukey HSD Test: Self-Concept of College Teachers – Academic Stream wise Comparison		
HSD[.05]=13.27		HSD[.01]=16.61
M1 vs M2 P<.01	M1 vs M3 P<.05	M2 vs M3 P<.01
M1 = mean of Sample 1 = Science	M2 = mean of Sample 2 = Commerce	M3 = mean of Sample 3 = Arts
HSD = the absolute [unsigned] difference between any two sample means required for significance at the designated level. HSD[.05] for the .05 level; HSD[.01] for the .01 level.		

Analysis of variance found that there was a statistically significant difference between the Self-Concept means of College Teachers of Science, Commerce and Arts Academic Streams ($F = 18.48, p < 0.0001$). The Tukey test found that the means for College Teachers of Science, Commerce and Arts Academic Streams (94.571, 128.486 and 110.971 respectively) were statistically significantly different from each other. The mean of the College Teachers of Commerce Stream were statistically significantly higher than the means of both the College Teachers of Science as well as those of Arts Streams. The mean of the College Teachers of Arts Stream were statistically significantly higher than the mean of the College Teachers of Science Stream. Thus, the null hypothesis (H_0-2) is rejected. The p-value indicates that the probability that the observed results are due to random chance is low.

Conclusions:

1. There is a statistically significant difference in the Self-Concept in Mumbai with reference to the sex of the College Teachers. The scores of Female College Teachers is statistically significantly greater than that of Male College Teachers. Thus, sex of the College Teachers seems to be a contributor to positive and greater favourable Self-Concept in Mumbai.
2. There is a statistically significant difference in the Self-Concept in Mumbai with reference to the Academic Stream of the College Teachers. The scores of College Teachers of Commerce Stream is statistically significantly greater than that of College Teachers of both Science and Arts Streams. The scores of College Teachers of Arts Stream is statistically significantly greater than that of College Teachers of Science Stream. Thus, Academic Stream (Science, Commerce and Arts) of the College Teachers seems to be a contributor to positive and greater favourable Self-Concept in Mumbai.

Summary of Major Findings of the Study:

- 1) Sex of the College Teachers seems to be a contributor to positive and greater favourable Self-Concept in Mumbai.
- 2) Academic streams of the College Teachers seems to be a contributor to positive and greater favourable Self-Concept in Mumbai.

Scope and Delimitations of the Present Study:

The above major findings of the study are constrained by the limited scope and delimitations of the research which were beyond the control of the researcher. These need to be taken into account, viz.:

- Standardised ready-made instrument (rating scale) has been employed for the ease of study.
- Paper-pencil test has been employed.
- Volunteering College Teachers participated in the study.
- Time period for data collection has been limited.
- Most of the College Teachers completed the scale at their convenience.
- Only three streams (Science, Commerce and Arts) were taken up for the study.
- Only South Mumbai area was considered for data collection.
- The Full Scale was considered in analysis rather than taking the two dimensions separately.

Significance of the Study:

The study, even though being a very short survey, highlights the fact that there is a significant difference in the Self-Concept of College Teachers of Mumbai with respect to their sex and academic streams. There is a significant favourable Self-Concept among Female College Teachers in Mumbai in comparison to their Male counterparts. There is also a significant favourable Self-Concept among College Teachers of Commerce Stream in comparison to those of the Science and Arts stream in Mumbai. Future

studies which are wider in scope and depth needs to be undertaken for a better understanding of the contemporary phenomena.

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